

Artificial Intelligence in English Language, Teaching and Learning: Opportunities, Challenges, and Practical Implications

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Abstract

English language has taken a massive change with the influence of Artificial intelligence. It enables the students to explore the learning platform and obtain immediate feedback related to writing and speaking. Subsequently it raises certain issues related to getting access to minute details, data privacy and constraints to limited in-depth learning. This paper deals with the use of AI in English teaching and throws light on the benefits and risks related in using the same. It indicates the positive use of AI when properly guided and monitored by the guidance of a teacher.

Key words: privacy, improvise, adaptive, monitoring,

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence is playing a pivotal role in modern English language teaching (ELT). It has been used by present day teachers to help students practise speaking, get feedback related to writing and understand the level of their knowledge on the concept and find ways to improvise their learning and understanding process. English being a globally recognized language is universally accepted and mastered by the entire human race.

AI has made teaching reach out to a large number of students to help master the language and improvise the way of speaking and writing in a positive manner. Not all students gain access to AI tools and in the same way the use of AI raises certain issues related to getting access to minute details, data privacy and constraints to the quality of learning.

This paper concentrates the use of AI in teaching learning process in schools, its benefits and challenges faced by the trainer and the learner and the ways by which it can be used wisely.

AI, a Tool in Language Learning

Artificial Intelligence is a computer system which thinks and learns the way humans do. It is used as tool by the teachers to modulate their teaching process based on the performance of the students. It can be termed as adaptive learning. This tool also supports in writing and getting immediate feedback, which can be termed as automated writing evaluation. It also helps the students in speaking activity by helping them pronounce the way using right diction and hence can be used as a speech recognition system.

It stimulates the conversation for practice. AI can analyse a student's performance and also guide them to formulate their content which fits their level. This constant monitoring and guiding system lent by AI enables the students to enhance their speaking skills in a right manner.

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Use of AI in English Language Teaching:

Artificial intelligence is used as a platform in different ways to enhance speaking and writing skills of each student. The various forms involved are adaptive learning, automated writing feedback, speaking and pronunciation and conversational practice.

Adaptive Learning

This platform adjusts itself based on the calibre of the student. The system identifies the area to be improved by the student and pays more attention to it. For example if the student seems to lag in grammatical part the system provides more exercise and ensures that concept is rightly understood and mastered by the ward. Studies shows that this mode of teaching has helped the child in a positive way and thus motivated for faster progress than the traditional teaching method.

Automated writing feedback

AI tool concentrates on the spellings, grammatical errors, vocabulary and sentence structuring in writing. In-case the student commits a mistake in any of these, the AI tool corrects them instantly thereby enabling the student to understand the errors and correct immediately. This mode helps the student to rectify their mistake and understand the nuances of writing.

This tool mainly focuses on grammar and word choice. It does not deal with creating a new content. They do not help or trigger the student to think and create new concept, hence it is mandatory for the students to get the guidance of the teacher to use the tool in the right manner.

Speaking and pronunciation

This tool concentrates on the intonation, stress and pronunciation. It analyses the student's way of pronouncing the words, the mode of stress and intonation. It helps the students to practice speaking en number of times without any fear. It helps in building confidence in them and improves their fluency in communicating content. Since AI tool is designed only for specific purpose, there might be instances where the tool fails to recognize certain accents. Hence it is mandatory to get the assistance of a teacher. The teacher's feedback has to be relied rather than the tool.

Conversational Practice

AI chat-bots enables students to practice conversing any time. They can stimulate interviews, discussions or daily conversations which helps the student to reduce tension in conversing. It also helps the student to increase the speed while communicating. Though it helps in speaking activity it does not fully understand the culture, tone or context. A real teacher is required to monitor the constant development of a student in speaking skills.

The Pros and Cons of Using AI in English Learning

The pros of using AI tool are that it helps in modulating the speaking and writing skills in a student. It makes learning more simple, stress free thereby providing opportunities for students and teachers to manage their

classes in a fruitful manner. In places where resources are limited, AI provides extra support that the teachers alone cannot offer.

The con is that not all student can have access to this tool or internet, so it might lead to a negative feeling in the minds of certain helpless children. Furthermore it focuses on limited areas like grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation etc. rather than critical or out of the box thinking. It also has certain restriction to communication as it sometimes fails to identify the accent of the speaker. It sometimes paves way for misusing of the tool by students to complete their assignments without understanding the concept. It also cannot to completely relied upon as it might raise the doubt of privacy.

Thus it is a fact that the use of AI has certain limitations and cannot replace a real teacher. The teacher's guidance and care in helping the child enhance proficiency in speaking and writing is mandatory.

Practical Suggestion in Using AI Tool in ELT: Some tips to enable using the AI tool in the right manner is as follows-

- The school management can take steps to train their teachers to use the AI tool so that they can use the tool for effective classroom teaching.
- They can design lessons using AI tool so that it helps the students to think out of the box and also communicate in the right manner.
- It should be ensured that the student's data are rightly collected, stored and used in a proper manner.
- Above all it should be ensured that all students get access to the tool.
- By following these rules it can be clear that the learning can be improved and simultaneously concentrate on human centered learning.

Conclusion

AI has set a modern trend to new classroom learning. It enables the students to explore the learning platform and obtain immediate feedback related to writing and speaking. It provides the student with the required amount of interest in mastering the concept. The use of AI if properly monitored by the teacher can create a drastic change in the teaching learning process. Any tool when used in the right manner will bring out the right output. Thus it is clear that in this modern era where thing move at a faster pace education is no different, it keeps taking a new out with the advent of new tools and technologies. The traditional method of teaching learning process has been replaced with modern technological tools.

References

- Bitchener, J., & Storch, N. (2022). *Automated writing evaluation in second language writing instruction*. Routledge.
- Brown, T. B., Mann, B., Ryder, N., Subbiah, M., Kaplan, J., Dhariwal, P., ... & Amodei, D. (2020). Language models are few-shot learners. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 33, 1877–1901.
- Chen, C.-M., & Xie, H. (2022). Intelligent adaptive learning systems in language education: A systematic review. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 60(6), 1023–1058.

- Heil, C. R., Wu, J. S., Lee, J. J., & Schmidt-Crawford, D. (2023). Artificial intelligence in education: Promises and implications for teaching and learning. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 26(1), 1–15.
- Hinkel, E. (2022). *Teaching English grammar in the age of AI and globalization*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kukulska-Hulme, A. (2021). *Mobile assisted language learning*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lancaster, T., & Cotarlan, C. (2021). Contract cheating by STEM students through a file-sharing website: A Covid-19 pandemic perspective. *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 17(1), 1–16.
- Li, T. (2021). Effects of automated writing evaluation feedback on L2 learners' writing. *Language Learning & Technology*, 25(1), 65–80.
- Li, Y., & Ni, Y. (2023). AI-enhanced ELT: Trends and challenges. *Computers & Education*, 181, 104455.
- Williamson, B., & Eynon, R. (2020). *AI in education and the future of learning*. Routledge.
- Woolf, B. P., Arroyo, I., & Tai, M. (2021). Personalized learning through adaptive AI systems. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*, 31(3), 403–425.
- Yu, V., & Almeroth, K. (2020). Data-driven analytics in adaptive language learning. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49(1), 5–24.
- Zhang, Y., & Han, J. (2025). Conversational AI and English speaking fluency. *Language Learning & Technology*, 29(2), 88–106.
- Zhou, Q., Singh, N., & Sutanto, J. (2024). Data privacy in AI educational systems. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 72(3), 200–219.